

FEATURES OF EDUCATIONAL MOTIVATION OF STUDENTS OF DIFFERENT EDUCATIONAL FIELDS

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Annotation. The article is devoted to the study of the characteristics of motivation of students studying in various fields of education. Particular attention is paid to such an aspect of this problem as stimulating the educational and professional activities of students of higher educational institutions.

Keywords. personal motivational sphere, motivation, learning motivation, structure of learning motivation, motivational activity of students in different educational areas.

Annotasiya. Maqolada turli ta'lim sohalarida tahsil oluvchi talabalarining o'quv faoliyati motivlarining o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan. Ushbu muammoning Oliy ta'lim muassasi talabalarining o'quv va kasbiy faoliyatini rag'batlantirish kabi jixatiga aloxida e'tibor qaratilmoqda.

Kalit so'zlar. shaxsning motivatsion soxasi, motivatsiya, o'quv motivatsiyasi, o'quv motivatsiyasining tuzulishi, turli ta'lim yo'nalishi talabalarining o'quv motivatsiya faoliyati.

Аннотация. Статья посвящена изучению особенностей мотивации студентов, обучающихся в различных сферах образования. Особое внимание уделяется такому аспекту данной проблемы, как стимулирование учебной и профессиональной деятельности студентов высших учебных заведений.

Ключевые слова. личностное мотивационная сфера, мотивация, мотивация обучения, структура мотивации обучения, мотивационная деятельность студентов разных образовательных направлений.

Educational activities include almost all the years of personality formation, starting from kindergarten and ending with education in secondary and higher vocational schools. Education is a necessary requirement for any person [1].

Despite the importance of this problem, the technologies of studying students' learning motivation are hardly considered by modern researchers. If necessary, it is necessary to know the motivational structure of students' educational activity in order to correct work methods and to form a positive motivation for studying, thus increasing the effectiveness of the educational process [2].

In the most general sense, activity motivation is understood as a set of driving forces that encourage a person to perform certain actions. These forces are located outside and inside of a person, forcing him to perform certain actions consciously or unconsciously [3]. At the same time, the connection between human influences and reactions to them depends on his life experience, upbringing and emotional state, as a result of which different people can react differently to the same influences [3]. Therefore, a more precise definition of motivation should be adopted [3].

“Motivation is a set of internal and external driving forces that encourage a person to act, determine the limits and forms of activity, and direct this activity to achieve certain goals” [3]. The influence of motivation on human behavior depends on many factors, it is mainly individual and can change due to feedback from human activity.

Educational motivation is a special type of motivation included in educational activities [4]. In a broader sense, learning motivation can be seen as the general name of processes, methods, tools of students for effective cognitive activity, active learning of educational content [5]. Like any other type of motivation, it is systematic and primarily characterized by orientation, stability and dynamics.

We came to the following conclusion regarding the study of the dependence of students' learning motivation on the fields of education (Table 1).

Table 1

The results of the study of the dependence of students' learning motivation on the fields of education (Kruskal-Wallis H-criterion)

Indicators	Average colors			H	p
	Social and humanities (N=1256)	Natural sciences (N=152)	Exact Sciences (N=363)		
Communicative motives	871,2	993,8	892,2	7,9	0,019*
Motivations to avoid failure	860,6	972,1	938,0	11,2	0,004**
Motives to achieve reputation	861,3	961,5	939,7	10,3	0,006**
Professional motives	867,5	989,4	906,6	8,5	0,014*
Motives for creativity	878,0	963,9	881,1	3,9	0,139
Learning motives	858,7	1018,1	925,0	15,9	0,000**

Social motives	859,5	971,6	941,7	12,0	0,003**
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Note:* - $p < 0.05$; ** - $p < 0.01$

As can be seen from the table, a number of differences in the level of confidence in the characteristics of learning motives among students studying in different fields of education were found. In particular, it was observed that there are differences in the level of confidence on the scale of communicative motives among students studying in different educational fields ($H=7.9$; $p < 0.05$). That is, we can observe that the students of natural sciences showed the highest results in terms of communicative motives. In most cases, communicative motives in the educational process refer to such characteristics as the students' response during the lesson and communication with the teacher. It is the natural and concrete sciences students who have high communicative motives in relation to learning, and the representatives of the humanities have low these motives. was determined to be. A look at admissions statistics shows that most humanities majors are more likely to follow the "no matter what major" principle, while those in the natural and concrete fields are more likely to strong industry knowledge and high level of motivation required. That's why their motives may have been high.

According to the results of the motives of avoiding failure, differences in the level of confidence among students studying in different fields of education were found ($H=11.2$; $p < 0.01$). In terms of avoiding failure, the highest indicators were recorded among students of natural sciences, followed by students of exact sciences and lastly students of social and humanities. Therefore, it can be concluded that among students studying in the field of natural and concrete sciences, motivations to avoid failure are more evident than among students studying in the social and humanitarian field.

Differences in the level of confidence among students studying in different fields of education were found based on the results of motives for achieving prestige ($H=10.3$; $p < 0.01$). The highest results in terms of motives for gaining prestige were recorded among students of natural sciences, while the lowest indicators were observed among students of social and humanitarian fields. In our opinion, as a result of the special attention paid to the field of natural sciences, these areas have a high reputation as promising career fields, and therefore, high results were noted in the requirements for the motivation to achieve prestige.

Figure 2.3.1. The results of the study of the dependence of students' learning motivation on the fields of education.

According to the results of the analysis of the scale of professional motives, differences in the level of confidence between students studying in different fields of education were determined ($H=8.5$; $p<0.05$). Here, too, we witnessed that students studying natural sciences showed the highest results. The predominance of professional motives among students studying natural sciences is definitely determined by the desire to become a mature specialist in the chosen field in the future. It is not surprising that students of natural sciences have a high need to become masters of their profession in the future, if this is determined by their attitude to their profession.

According to the results of the comparative analysis of learning motives, differences in the level of confidence between students studying in different fields of education were found ($H=15.9$; $p<0.01$). Here, too, the fact that students in the fields of natural sciences are distinguished by high indicators of learning motivation is attracting attention. In the next place, students studying in specific subjects, and in the last place, students studying in social and humanitarian directions, are observed to show learning motives. The fact that students of natural sciences record high results in this result certainly indicates that they strive to study, that is, to expand their knowledge as much as possible, to acquire deep knowledge in the process of education.

According to the results of the comparative analysis of the scale of social motives, differences in the level of confidence were found between students studying in different fields of education ($H=12.0$; $p<0.05$). According to this

scale, it is noted that the results of students of natural sciences are higher than those of other areas. Social motives are related to the need to communicate with people, to help other people, to show kindness, and to look good. the high level of these motives among students of natural sciences indicates the existence of needs for social relations.

If we carefully observe the results presented above, it was noted that almost all of the students' educational motivation is high in the students studying in the natural sciences. Therefore, it can be concluded that students of natural sciences are distinguished by higher educational motivation compared to students of other fields.

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